

INVESTIGATING THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITES MADE OF COCONUT LEAVES FIBRE REINFORCEMENT AND POLYESTER MATRIX

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ABSTRACT

A set of changes have been brought to the procedure of manufacturing composites, consisting of coconut leaf fibre reinforcement in a polyester matrix, in order to improve their tensile strength. The fibres were first coated with a polyester resin. Two factors were then varied, namely, the amount of shell powder and coconut leaves fibre. Moreover, a weaving configuration of the fibre was used.

The tensile strength of the composite was observed to increase with the fibre content. The largest tensile strength of the composite was observed to be 49.2 MPa, which was a 130 % improvement over the plain plastic material.

KEYWORDS

Coconut fibres; polyester; coconut shell; tensile strength

INTRODUCTION

Coconut trees grow abundantly in Mauritius and its dependencies, including Agalega Islands and Rodrigues Island. Coconut palms require a continuous supply of water, which can be provided by rainfall of the order of 2000 mm per annum, or from groundwater (at a depth of 1–3 m), although they cannot tolerate waterlogging. They grow best at average temperatures of around 26–27°C and their growth is stimulated by a sufficient supply of chlorine in the soil (Verma and Gope, 2015) Hence, they are particularly suitable for the small Mascarene islands of the Indian Ocean. In the Agalega Islands, they are cultivated over around 800 hectares. Moreover, there is a plan to increase the coconut cultivation to 1500 hectares (Veer-Ramjeawon & Chan, 2010). Based on a study performed by the Mauritius Research Council (MRC) and the Outer Islands Development Corporation (OIDC), coconut oil has been considered as a substitute for diesel for transportation and generation of electricity in the island.

There are three main types of coconut species available in Mauritius: Pemba, Ceylan, and Malayan Dwarf. When growing conditions are favourable, the 'Ceylan' produces large varieties with larger husk sizes than the other species. The fruit of Dwarf palms, on the other hand, is typically smaller than that of tall palms (Tnau Agritech Portal, 2020).

Taking into consideration the large amount of coconuts being harvested locally, several SMEs have grown and are involved in developing coconut based products including, cosmetics, oil, refreshing coconut water and food. It should also be noted that much waste is also generated when maintaining coconut trees in hotels and coastal regions. The use of coconut in the island has also led to considerable waste, such as coconut husk and shell, which are eventually dumped and rarely used for other purposes. One of the ways to make sustainable use of the coconut husk, shell and leaves is to manufacture composites with the coconut fibres. This will eventually lead to a permanent solution for the waste disposal problem.

Coconut fibres are abundant, versatile, renewable, inexpensive, and biodegradable and can be used to make a wide range of products (Kumar Naik, 2018). Furthermore, coconut fibers have been discovered

to be the most ductile of all natural fibers, with a strain capacity of 4 to 6 times that of other natural fibers (Ede and Aina, 2015). Fibers are typically extracted from both green and matured brown coconuts. The amount of lignin in the coconut increases as it matures. However, according to Basak et al. (1983) after treatment, both have little difference in their mechanical properties. Similarly, Satyanarayana et al. (1986) found no significant differences in the crystal structure of green and brown (fully matured) leaves.

Recently, much effort was made to develop bio-based products (Thinkohkaew et al., 2020) for several industries, including the automotive industry, the IT industry and medical technology. Natural fibers have several benefits, namely low density, high biodegradability, fair specific strengths and strong sound reduction (Chandramohan and Marimuthu, 2011). In addition, these fibres may be incinerated for power recycling at the end of their life cycle since its calorific value is strong (Hwang, 2016; Chandramohan and Marimuthu, 2011). Natural fibres are non-toxic, globally usable, cost effective and environment friendly, as opposed to synthetic fibres. Coconut fibres, though they are not as strong as many other natural fibres, they are able to take strain 4-6 times more than them. Other advantages of coconut fibres can be summarized as follows (Sen and Reddy 2011):

- They are light and strong.
- They can easily withstand heat.
- They can withstand saline water.
- The use of coconut fibres seems to delay the plastic shrinkage controlling crack development at early ages.
- Coir is an abundant, renewable and cost-effective.

Unfortunately, the performance of coconut fibres as a reinforcement in polymer composites is unsatisfactory and not comparable even with other natural fibres due to its low cellulose content (36–43%), high lignin content (41–45%) and high microfibrillar angle (Rout et al., 2001). However, the strength of the composites can be improved in several ways. All natural fibres are hydrophilic in nature [Bledki et al., 1996; Rout et al., 2001; Hasan et al., 2021]. The internal adhesion can be improved by modifying the surface topology of fibres by a suitable pre-treatment or by selecting the proper components of the bonding system. One method is the alkali treatment of the fibres.

It has been observed by Rout et al. (2001) that 2% alkali treated coir composites show better tensile strength (26.80 MPa) whereas 5% alkali treated coir composites show better flexural and impact strength (Rout et al., 2001). Chemical treatment of coconut fibre increases the cellulose content, but hemicelluloses, lignin and other materials content decreases compared to untreated (raw) coconut fibre (Suresh Kumar et al., 2014). The composite made of treated fibres show higher tensile, flexural and impact strengths compared to the one made of untreated fibres. The interfacial bond between fibre and matrix was improved in treated composite (Suresh Kumar et al., 2014). Alkali treatment reduces fibre diameter and thereby increases the aspect ratio. Therefore, the development of a rough surface topography and enhancement in aspect ratio offer better fiber–matrix interface adhesion and an increase in mechanical properties (Mohanty et al., 2001; Mishra et al., 2001). Consequently, mercerization or more general alkali treatment had a lasting effect on the mechanical behavior of coir fibers, especially on fiber strength and stiffness (Bledzki and Gassan 1999). Other methods to improve interfacial bonds include the use of silane (Atiqah et al. 2017).

To reduce the disposal problems of coconut leaves in Mauritius, the use of the coconut leaf fibres in composites could be considered as a sustainable solution. In this study, the improvement of the mechanical properties of the composite consisting of coconut leaf fibres and polyester matrix would be investigated for a more effective use of the product. This was performed by testing the treated and polyester coated fibres with powdered coconut shell and a weaving configuration of the fibres in the composite. It is expected that the resulting composite would have improved properties as compared to those consisting of only treated fibres. Hence, the range of applications of the composites is expected to increase.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Fibres were extracted from Ceylan coconut leaves. In the case of fibre treatments, 5% wt NaOH solution, based on Oushabi et al. (2017), was used for the extraction of the fibres.

The treated fibres were then coated with a polyester coating. Two treatments were performed to improve the mechanical properties of the composite were considered in this study:

- Use of powdered coconut shell together with the leaf fibres.
- Use of a weaving configuration of the fibres in the matrix.

Coconut fiber (CF) preparation

Branches (around 130 cm in length) from the Ceylan tree were cut and sectioned into 4 parts, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Coconut leaves

The stalk was opened and the fibrous tissue was removed and immersed in water overnight before the fibre was extracted, thus loosening the fibres and allowing easy removal. The fibres were then rinsed to remove dirt or any other impurities before being subjected to oven drying at 60°C for 24 hours. The resulting fibres obtained are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Removal of fibers from leaf stalks

The coconut fibres were chemically treated using 5% wt NaOH.

Treatment of the fibres

Surface coating of fibers using polyester resin

Polyester resin was utilized for the surface coating of treated fibers to increase the bonding between the CF reinforcement and the matrix. The fibres were coated by immersing them in small groups into the resin. After coating, they were oven dried for 24 hours at 60°C.

At this point three types of fibres used for tests were: untreated fibres (type 1), treated fibres (type 2) and treated and coated fibres (type 3).

Diameter measurement before tensile testing

The diameter of the fibres were determined by micrometry using a metallurgical microscope, with 50x magnification. Diameter measurements were taken at 5 different locations along the fibre length. The fibres were rotated and the diameter was measured at four points over the cross-section of the fibre to determine whether it is circular so as to minimize experimental errors. The same steps were repeated for all batch of fibers subjected to the tests.

Tensile Testing of Fibres

The tensile test was performed according to ASTM C1557-14 (2014). The Testometric M500-50 AT Universal Testing Machine was used to conduct the test. The gauge length was set at 25.4 mm, and the fibre length was verified to be at least 1.5 times the gauge length. A steady speed of 8 mm/min was selected so that the highest strength at fracture was attained in less than 30 seconds with a 20 N load cell.

Mould Manufacturing Process

Test specimens were manufactured in accordance with ASTM D638-14 (2014), with a thickness of 6 mm. The grid size was varied for various fibre loadings as shown on Table 1.

Table1: Grid Size values

<i>Fibre loading (% wt.)</i>	<i>~Grid size (cm x cm)</i>
<i>0.5</i>	1.8 x 1.8
<i>1.0</i>	0.9 x 0.9
<i>1.5</i>	0.5 x 0.5

Tensile test of samples

The tensile tests were performed according to ASTM D638-14. Each tests were performed in sets of five. The samples had to break within the gauge length and they had to fracture in less than 5 min.

The percentage weight of the powdered coconut shell and that of the coconut fibre were varied and the optimum combination was determined. The most significant treatment was also determined through Taguchi analysis. The maximum fibre content was restricted to 1.5 wt% as it was not possible to increase the fibre content further.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The diameter of the leaf fibres are shown in Table 2. The diameter for the treated fibres is lesser than that of the untreated fibres. This has been observed in all studies performed on natural fibres. The diameter is also in accordance with the results obtained in other studies on coconut fibres. This is due to the fact that the treatment removes the impurities and waxy materials all around the fibre. Similar results have been obtained by Mei-po et al. (2011), Yan et al. (2014), Essabira et al. (2016), Filho et al. (2005), Ramakrishna & Sundararajan (2005) and Sliseris et al. (2016).

Table 2: Result of diameter for each group of fibers

Type of fibre	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3
Diameter/mm	0.719	0.375	0.551
SD	0.124	0.096	0.136

The results for the tensile tests, performed in accordance with ATSM C1557 – 14, are shown in Table 3. This is also in accordance with other studies (Dicker et al. ,2014; Yan et al., 2014; Li et al., 2007; Sliseris et al., 2016). The tensile strength is even much larger than some reported by some researchers (Verma & Gope, 2015; Sen & Reddy 2011)

Table 3: Tensile test result

Type of fibre	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3
Mean Tensile Strength /MPa	67.689	138.801	145.886
Standard Deviation	27.45	64.329	106.691

Tensile Test

Figure 3 shows the fractured samples after performing the tensile tests.

Figure 3: Fractured samples within gage length

Tensile test result

Table 4 shows the mean tensile strength measured while varying the fibre content (Factor A) and powder content (Factor B).

Table 4: Mean Tensile strength for various factors and levels.

		<i>Factor A- Fibre content (%wt)</i>		
		<i>0.5</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>1.5</i>
	<i>2</i>	<i>38±3</i>	<i>28±3</i>	<i>32±2</i>

<i>Factor B - Power content (%wt)</i>	3	31±3	28±3	40±3
	4	32±2	28±4	49±4

As per Devaraju et al., the powder proved to be effective in dispersing the loads along the composite. The mean tensile strength of the plain specimens was 21.4 MPa, which is higher than that of Owen et al. The highest tensile strength value was observed to be 49.2 MPa with a fibre content of 1.5 wt% and powder content of 4wt%. This is a 130 % improvement over the plain composite. This is much higher than those reported by Mohanty et al. (2001), Jayabal et al. (2013), dos Santos et al. (2018), Liu et al. (2019), Priya et al. (2014) and Júnior et al. (2010).

Nevertheless, in order to determine the most important factor of the two parameters which produces the best composite strength, the Taguchi DOE approach was used. The two parameters (A and B) were varied at three levels, based on Table 4. Table 5 is a summary of the Taguchi results.

Table 5: Summary for Taguchi

Factors	Degree of Freedom	Sum of Square	Mean Square	F-value
A	2	14.674	7.337	4.901
B	2	0.993	0.497	0.332
Interaction	4	7.990	1.998	
Total	(k-1) = (9-1) = 8	23.657		

As the F value of factor A is higher than that of factor B, factor A can be considered to be the most significant factor. The fibre content therefore has the most leading effect on composite's tensile strength.

CONCLUSION

The tensile strength of treated coconut fiber reinforced polyester composite was investigated in order to look into the possibility of using waste coconut leaves and shell. The composites were manufactured based on two factors, each with three levels. The findings demonstrated that as fibre content was increased, tensile strength significantly improved. Similar patterns were supported by results from existing studies. For tensile strength, 1.5 percent fiber content with 4% wt. powder was found to be optimal, with fibre content being the most important factor. The greatest tensile strength value was observed to be 49.2 MPa. This was a 130 % improvement over the plain plastic material. It is also much higher than those reported in other studies.

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